

Title:

Indoor Environmental Quality: Balancing Thermal Comfort, Energy Efficiency, Infection Control and Air Pollution in Indian Cities.

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The Energy Conservation Movement in the world was tipped off by the Oil Crisis of the 1973(Hobday & Dancer, 2013). This was a time where the West started to think of saving energy due to supply issues from the Middle East. The outcome of this movement was most beneficial for Developing countries as they could start fresh and clean in their growth stories. They had the option of developing without repeating what the west had done, i.e., indiscriminate use of fossil fuel for industry and growth. India, as a developing country has ventured in this and energy conservation has become part of the common parlance.

With energy conservation as a goal in the built environment, multiple Green Building consultants brought in the best computer simulation experts who optimized built spaces, treating them as mechanical zones which had to be engineered. This created excellent results in providing just the right thermal comfort with the maximum savings. But, often overlooked was the Indoor Air quality, as a decreased energy use meant recycling cool air and decreasing the air changes per hour. Often discussed is the Sick Building Syndrome which was an outcome of this energy optimized building. Recirculation of air became a norm which led to an increase in the gas concentrations in the indoor environments. The rise in air pollution in the Indian cities, further strengthened this practice of recirculation as the outside air was 'foul' and the air inside was kept isolated with rounds of filtration and refiltration. GRIHA, very proactively addressed this with an increased stress on the monitoring of the Indoor Air quality with a recommendation for using Carbon Dioxide meters in the indoor spaces to have effective ventilation and fresh air supply.

But as evolution goes, this was soon challenged by the COVID crisis where fresh air was to be brought in not only for gas exchange, but also for the dilution effect caused by ventilation on the microbial concentrations in the indoor spaces. In dilution ventilation, the fresh air flushes out the microbial concentration in the inside space with the outdoor space making the chance of transmission in congested spaces lesser. (Escombe et al., 2007; Richardson, Morrow, Kalil, Bekker, & Wood, 2014)This is the most cost effective way as it sometimes requires just a simple intervention of opening the windows.(Cox et al., 2012) This effect has been very widely studied by research done on Tuberculosis and its spread. Tuberculosis or TB is an airborne infection which spreads from one

person to another through the small droplets which a person emits while talking. (Issarow, Mulder, & Wood, 2015) These droplets infect another person in the proximity who inhales them. These droplets increase in number when a person coughs or sneezes. Tuberculosis has remained in Human for thousands of years and we have become a very reliable reservoir for this disease. (Lougheed, 2017) In the latent state, the TB can infect a person without any symptom and he can get the symptoms later in life due to ageing or immunosuppression. He then becomes a spreader, unknowingly most of the time. With COVID, there is a large body of researchers which are continuously researching on the airborne transmission of the disease. The research done on TB for decades is constantly becoming relevant to decrease the spread of diseases like COVID.

India has multiple climate zones. In the composite climate for example, there are spells of extreme heat and extreme cold. Our lives, which are increasingly being spent indoors, are getting permanently influenced by the Thermal Comfort which the air conditioner provides. There have been many successful attempts for a lucky few to get buildings which are passively designed and have thermal comfort within the adaptive range. But most, if not all buildings today are increasingly being designed with a pre thought provision for air conditioning systems. In some new design and most retrofit designs where Air conditioner is introduced, the designer remains clueless in providing for optimal air changes per hour into the spaces. The problem of fresh air supply is solved to an extent in the centralized air conditioning systems with air handling units where air changes are possible. This is almost impossible to be done when a split AC is prescribed which has no mechanism for fresh air supply into the room. This situation is made worse by the use of hermetically sealed window and door frames which reduce any air “leakage” which would have otherwise provided some fresh air as a blessing in disguise. Increasingly, HVAC engineers are prescribing Ultraviolet Germicidal Irradiation technology which kills the microbes in the Air Handling Unit. (Escombe et al., 2009) This may be appropriate for sterile settings but the cost of this technology for all domestic buildings may be prohibitive. On another front, current research in total sterilization, discourages the use of a complete ‘slash and burn’ as done in UVGI as we may need certain sets of microbes to keep us healthy. (Kembel et al., 2012, 2014) This is further supported by the Hygiene Hypothesis which is built around the fact that over sanitization may make us vulnerable when we may move to spaces with higher microbe concentrations. These spaces may just be outside the door of our ultra clean and private air bubbles (Gardiner, 2020) There is further research being done in creating standards for optimum levels of permissible microbial flora in the indoor environments.

These private bubbles may serve us well in another area where Indian cities have topped the charts. This is the problem which we constantly dismiss by stating the excuse of the developmental aspirations. (SPEARS, 2019) This is the problem of air pollution which we often shroud in the growth numbers in terms of electrified villages and multinational factories set up. Our electricity production in India is largely through the Coal powered plants and we have a long way to go to make a

substantial switch to Renewable Energy. Even if all the cities in the country, as often touted, switch to Electric Vehicles, we would still be using a fossil fuel to produce the electricity to run it. (Smedley, 2020) We may solve urban pollution levels in Delhi, but that will be offset by a rising pollution level in a small town where the coal powered electricity project will be located. A switch to renewable energy is a must to make sure our windows in the cities can open for the good reason of “fresh” air supply and infection control due to dilution.

Studies done in isolation on Thermal comfort may neglect fresh air supply. Studies done on fresh air supply and infection control due to ventilation may miss Air pollution in the studies. Studies on Air Pollution alone may put a dent on the energy performance of a building.

The Holy Grail for Indian cities lies in creating Indoor Environments which can optimize Energy Performance with Thermal Comfort, Infection Control with Air Pollution and so on. The problems can be identified and solved once they are acknowledged. They are acknowledged once they are measured and they can be measured only when the society reaches a tipping point where the only way to go is through the problem, which sometimes takes us back to where we all started.

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